

Kingsway International Christian Center

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Kingsway International Christian Centre (KICC), was established in September 1992 by Nigerian-born Pastor Matthew Ashimolowo. It began with about 300 members at Holloway Boys' School in North London. The growth was so rapid that within a year they bought a 3-storey property for 1,000 people capacity. By 1995 membership hit 3,000 and they were running 3 services a day. In 1996 KICC opened branches in South West London and began TV broadcasting. By 1997 they held 4 Sunday services at Darnley Road plus services at Hackney Empire, Hackney Central Hall, and York Hall, with membership in the 4,000 and since then the growth has been tremendous. KICC is described as one of the largest growing churches in Western Europe, Nigeria and some part of the world. Sunday attendance at the main church at Prayer City in Buckmore Park, Chatham, Kent ME5 9QG reaches up to 12,000 people. At KICC Prayer City Sunday services are held at 9.00 am, 12 noon, and the evening service is at 6 pm. KICC Nigeria, serving as the Nigerian headquarters, is headquartered in Maryland, Lagos, and operates over 20 branches nationwide under the leadership of National Superintendent Pastor Femi Faseru. There is also King's Kids programme for children aged 5-12, TNT programme as teenage meetings for 13-18 year olds and KYAM programme for young adults aged 19-30 years old. An ever-increasing number of people continue to attend its Sunday services, exciting events and special programmes at KICC headquarters, branches and chapels. The congregation is predominantly West African, under 50 years old, with worshippers from 46 nations. The ministry focuses on Bible teaching, fervent prayer, prosperity-oriented evangelism, counseling, and community support. Beyond church services, KICC runs significant community and humanitarian efforts, feeding tens of thousands and providing empowerment initiatives across Europe and Africa. In the Media it has launched KICC TV, the UK's first church-owned TV channel. Ashimolowo's Winning Ways_Program airs on TBN, God TV, Premier Radio, and host of others in Nigeria, across Africa, Europe, America etc. In the area of education KICC is the proprietor of Kings University, Ode-Omu, Osun State, in Nigeria. The Church is a Charismatic/Pentecostal ministry. Its foundational tenets include the divine inspiration of the Bible, the Trinity, salvation through Jesus Christ, and the baptism of the Holy Spirit. Central to its ethos are doctrines of faith, prosperity, and evangelism. KICC believes in one God existing in three persons: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. The Bible is regarded as the infallible, inspired, and authoritative Word of God. The Church teaches the fall of Humanity and in need of redemption. They believe salvation and reconciliation to God come exclusively through the substitutionary death and shed blood of Jesus Christ. The church teaches that believers are resurrected to everlasting life in heaven, while unbelievers face eternal punishment. The Key Principles and Practices includes The "Faith" Movement which is heavily influenced by Word of Faith teachings, KICC emphasizes that believers access God's promises through positive confession and a high level of faith. They believe God operates according to the measure of a

believer's faith rather than the size of their need. KICC teaches that God desires holistic prosperity—spiritual, physical, and financial. The ministry focuses heavily on "covenant practices" such as tithing and generous giving as biblical principles to unlock supernatural financial increase and wealth creation. The church's overarching motto is "Raising Champions and Taking Territories." It strongly emphasizes personal development, leadership, and success to help members fulfil their God-given potential in all spheres of life. KICC views the church's mandate as not just spiritual, but also transformational. Members are encouraged to be active witnesses (often referred to as "evangelists"), and the church places importance on exercising spiritual gifts, including healing and prophecy.

Date Range: 1992 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ashimolowo, Matthew. *The Coming Wealth Transfer: Believing the Prophecy, Applying the Principles, Preparing to Be a Millionaire*. London: Mattyson Media, 2006.
- Source 2: Ashimolowo, Matthew. *101 Truths About Divine Success*. London: Mattyson Media Co, 1997.
- Source 3: Ashimolowo, Matthew. *31 Secrets to a Successful Marriage*. London: Mattyson Media Co, 1998.

Notes: KICC claims that there are over 90 publications on the biblical principles of the Ministry

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: www.kce.kicc.org.uk/wp-content
- Source 1 Description: Ashimolowo, Matthew. "Kings College of Excellence Prospectus."
- Source 2 URL: www.kicc.org.uk/church/statement-of-faith
- Source 2 Description: Ashimolowo, Matthew. "Statement of Faith."
- Source 3 URL: www.kicc.org.uk/church/kicc-vision
- Source 3 Description: Ashimolowo, Matthew. "kick vision."

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: www.kicconline.org/our-beliefs

– Source 1 Description: Ashimolowo, Matthew. "Our Core Values & Beliefs"

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: KICC engages with other religious groups mainly through community outreach. Their charity works are sometimes extended to other members of other religious groups such as Muslims and adherents of the African Traditional Religions

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: KICC's contact with other religious groups doesn't appear to be competitive because their outreach especially to other religion are presentable as charitable

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: It is very accommodating and pluralistic as their outreach are not seen as proselytising or interfaith rivalry

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: their cultural contact appears largely neutral and service oriented rather than confrontational and overly partisan. their activities suggests neutral in practice focused on social support

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: no evidence that KICC itself is involved in violent conflicts within area of existence

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Through conviction, baptism and participation in all Christian obligations of the group through voluntary participation. However, it records affiliation only for its own members who register. it doesn't assign or change the religious affiliation of others by force

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: KICC is an independent Pentecostal Church. Like most Pentecostal churches membership is voluntary and based on personal profession of faith and registration with the Church

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: membership is by profession of Faith and it is voluntary

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: The group does not practice class-based membership system. KICC membership is by faith and it is voluntary

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: KICC membership is not assigned by age. It has the majority of its members under 50 years old, but that's a description of who attends not a rule for membership

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Both Male and Female, old and young attends the religious group

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Full membership of the KICC is by voluntary decision of would-be members to undergo baptism by immersion.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Through membership by choice through baptism and financial involvement

Notes: Through membership by choice, profession of faith, baptism and financial obligations

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is core to KICC mission. every member is expected to be an evangelist to propagate the mission. they run outreaches like hospital, hospice, prison visit, counseling career and other legal services. it was claimed that membership grew from 300 to thousands. KICC actively seeks new membership through evangelism and outreaches

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: All members are expected to carry out the proselytizing not just professionals

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: KICC trains professionals for mission work but it is voluntary

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: It is not mandatory for all adherent, but by choice. However, the mission work is regarded as all adherents responsibilities

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: It is not coercive but by choice and as voluntary obligations

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: No evidence of official government support from KICC. However, its founder Pastor Matthew Ashimolowo has publicly supported the current political administration in Nigeria

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: KICC has a conception of apostasy, but it's framed in typical Pentecostal/evangelical terms rather than as a formal church legal category

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to records available it is estimated around 200,000 membership

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.5

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: KICC has recognized leaders at both global and regional level. the leadership include Founder & Senior Pastor, Nigerian Leadership, Family leadership such Pastor Yemisi Ashimolowo serves as Resident Pastor in some KICC branches while their son Pastor Tobi Ashimolowo was anointed as Resident Pastor in the United Kingdom Church

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

Notes: Based on the structure of group there are 4 main levels in the leadership hierarchy namely Global/Founder level, National/Regional level, Branch/Local level and Ministry/Departmental Level

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: Within KICC's Pentecostal context, leaders are believed to operate with supernatural gifting, but not to possess supernatural power in their own right. they believe that Holy Spirit gives supernatural gifts. So members typically believe that leader operate with supernatural gifting and authority from God

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Through faith, Personal devotion and personal spiritual encounter with the Supreme being.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: it is believed that spiritual powers and Supernatural gifts come from God through impartation and not passed on like a cultural trait from one person to another. It is only administrative power that can be passed on

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: KICC determine administrative office based on the spiritual or supernatural gifts possessed by individuals

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: KICC appoint their leaders but not by congregational votes like some Churches. New Pastors and National superintendents are appointed by the senior leadership

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: But this only happen in the case of the senior leadership of the Church

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the

selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: KICC doctrine treats its leadership as fallible and not infallible. They teach that all humans, including pastors, are subject to errors and sin, which leaders can be rebuked, corrected or removed if they violate doctrine or conduct in manners not acceptable to the group's ethos as directed by the Holy Spirit.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: On administrative matters, followers are expected obey, but on spiritual matters, the Church emphasizes personal responsibility; members are told to test prophecies, spiritual instructions and teachings against the scriptures

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: JUst like any Christian denominations KICC uses the Christian Canon Bible

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Scriptures and tradition are both written and oral

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is believed to have been written by men and women who were inspired by the power of the Holy Spirit over the period of thousands years and later canonised

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Not after the Canonisation process in about 365AD

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The Bible is written in different languages of the adherent, however, its hermeneutics are being regulated by Christian leadership of each denomination

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: KICC has a Prayer City in Chatham Kent: it is their main site. They purchased and converted a large former secular building into their UK headquarters which has about 12,000 people in attendance every Sunday. In Nigeria, they have places of worship and other properties which facilitate their spiritual ambitions.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 2

Notes: Just a fraction of the city

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 97124

Notes: It sits on 24 acre site, approximately 97,124m square meter

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 8094

Notes: The total site is 24 acres of land that has 12 large buildings plus 2 foundations in average that is about 8,094 square meter per building

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 24

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: There schools for training their religious leaders, children and Youths, the building for prayer convergence all in 12 large buildings plus 2 foundation

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: KICC doesn't use traditional iconography like icons, statues, or images of saints in worship. They avoid religious iconography because of the biblical command against graven images

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: For KICC, Prayer city in Chatham, Kent is treated as the main site dedicated to sacred practice. Because the founder is Nigerian by birth, his church is also present in Nigeria and has a following especially among the upwardly mobile adults and young adults. They are a Pentecostal group comprised of middle class Nigerians mostly in urban centres and cities in Nigeria

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: KICC doesn't orient its sacred site around natural or environmental features like a shrine at

a mountain, spring, or grove, because Prayer city is a converted facility not purpose-built sacred landscape. its orientation is functional and not symbolic

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: KICC does not promote pilgrimage to holy sites such as Mecca, Lourdes or Jerusalem. However, people attend large conferences, conventions, and prayer programme like KICC Annual Convention and Night of bliss where people attend from across the UK, Europe and Africa. But KICC frames it as attending a conference and convention, not visiting a site that's inherently holy

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The church believes the spirit, body and soul are three distinct parts of the human body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:
– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: KICC is a Pentecostal, Evangelical Church, and their doctrine follows mainstream Evangelical teachings on Life after death, and resurrection and judgement,

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes heaven where resurrection and judgement will occur

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that afterlife will be in heaven and hell which are not necessarily within the current human geographical abode.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The doctrine of the Church rejects reincarnation because of the biblical teaching they follow that after a man dies the next is judgement which will determine where his souls spends eternity

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: They immediately bury the corpse with a brief rite of passage

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are central to KICC's theology

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God is the central focus of KICC, because the church is a Trinitarian Pentecostal Church which believe that God is Supreme and singular but manifested in three entity. He is God, eternal, omnipresence, omnipotent omniscient and creator of all

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: KICC teaches that God is not inherently anthropomorphic, even though the Bible uses anthropomorphic language figuratively

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: KICC does not teach that supreme God is fused with any monarch. rather they teach that God and human rulers are separate. They teach that God is transcendent and sovereign over all earthly authority

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: KICC does not see monarch as manifestation or emanation of the high god. according to its belief, God manifested in Jesus Christ alone as "the Word became flesh". God created human distinct from himself. There is no divine substance in humans that makes a monarch a partial emanation from God. However, KICC teaches Romans 13:1-2 -

that government and authority are established by God for order and justice. But that is authority delegated not essence shared

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: KICC does not teach that the supreme high God is a kin relation to elites specifically. they see God as father to all believers, not just elites and reject lineage based privilege

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: He is eternal

Notes: The Supreme high God is eternal

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: KICC teaches that God did not only create the world but He directs its affairs and also will determines its end

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s)

within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He Knows its beginning and when the world will end

Notes: KICC teaches that GOd has power over this world because he is the

creator, He knows its beginning and the end of it

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Kingsway International Christian Centre (KICC), led by Pastor Matthew Ashimolowo, teaches that the supreme, almighty God exhibits positive emotions. Through their beliefs and teachings on the Fatherhood of God, KICC emphasizes that God is a loving, compassionate, and benevolent being whose core nature is defined by His positive attributes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

Notes: KICC generally aligns with the broader Word of Faith movement, which emphasizes that God's nature is steadfast, perfect, and characterized by faith and love rather than unstable, reactive human emotions.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: No, KICC and orthodox Christian theology do not teach that the supreme God possesses human physical hunger. In Christian teaching, God is an omnipotent and self-sufficient spirit who does not require physical sustenance. However, KICC leaders frequently teach about spiritual hunger—the desperate, human desire and passion for a deeper relationship with God, prayer, and His word

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Kingsway International Christian Centre (KICC) does not teach that it is permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the High God. Like traditional Pentecostal and evangelical churches, KICC strictly adheres to monotheism. KICC's doctrine mandates that worship, adoration, and prayer be directed solely to the Triune God: God the Father, God the Son (Jesus Christ), and God the Holy Spirit. According to their Statement Of Faith, the Bible is the ultimate infallible authority. Consequently, they strictly forbid the worship of any other entities, such as angels or demonic powers.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: immortality, love, Holy

Notes: KICC teaches that God possesses many features. In line with orthodox Christian

theology, KICC teaches that the Supreme High God is a Spirit who embodies attributes such as Omnipotence (all-powerful), Omniscience (all-knowing), Omnipresence (everywhere at all times), unconditional love, mercy, and sovereignty

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through the religious leader

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: KICC does not teach or promote divination practices. They regard divination—such as tarot cards, fortune-telling, and horoscopes—as unbiblical and warn against these practices. Instead, the ministry focuses on standard Christian teachings, including prosperity, prayer, spiritual warfare, and faith in God for supernatural breakthroughs.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through Prayers and Meditations

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through corporate prayers

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They have memory of past events; good or bad, could take revenge etc
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: Through Spiritual leader
-
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal

essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omniscience, Omnipotent and Omnibenevolence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in

public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He knows the supernatural because he created them all

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: He is powerful and supreme

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: prayers, revelations and the scriptures

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

- No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

- No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

- No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

- No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: the concept of supernatural monitoring is present in the teachings of KICC, but it is taught primarily as spiritual warfare against evil forces rather than a literal action by God. In KICC doctrine, particularly in teachings by Pastor Matthew Ashimolowo, supernatural monitoring operates in two main ways; 1. KICC teaches that "monitoring spirits" are demonic entities assigned by the forces of darkness to observe, track, and report on believers' lives to steal blessings or cause delays. Members are often led to

pray against and bind these spiritual entities and 2. Conversely, God is presented as the supreme, all-seeing protector. While God is not a "monitoring spirit," KICC teachings emphasize that He watches over His people to ensure their victory and protect them from the plans of the enemy

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Yes. Supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence is a prominent theme in the teaching of the KICC. The church emphasizes that followers are under the continuous surveillance of God, who intimately monitors their actions, thoughts, and adherence to moral norms

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: KICC does not teach that the Christian supernatural (God) cares about or is bound by local cultural taboos. Rather, KICC teaches that believers live under a "New Covenant" governed by grace rather than strict adherence to traditional or cultural restrictions

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: the Kingsway International Christian Centre (KICC) teaches that God, as a supernatural being, cares deeply about the murder of believers. The church teaches that the targeted persecution and murder of Christians (coreligionists) is a severe tragedy that offends God

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Bestiality, Homosexuality and polygamy

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In KICC/Kingdom teaching, “D9” usually refers to Domain 9: Oaths, Covenants & Legalities in the Spirit Realm. And supernatural beings do _ care deeply about oaths. KICC teaches that God is a covenant-keeping God. Angels are “ministering spirits” Heb 1:14, but they also execute judgment and enforcement of divine decrees. When one makes an oath/vow to God, heaven records it. Ecclesiastes 5:4-5 is the go-to verse: “When you make a vow to God, do not delay to fulfill it.”

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: In KICC/Kingdom teaching, supernatural beings do care about laziness. KICC teaches from Proverbs 22:29 – “Do you see a man diligent in his business? He will stand before kings.” Diligence, excellence, and “doing all things unto the Lord” Col 3:23 are seen as spiritual currency. Angels are ministering spirits Heb 1:14, but they’re also called “executors of God’s word” Psalm 103:20. So when you’re diligent + obedient, heaven backs you. Laziness = no legal ground for angels to enforce blessing. “Faith without works is dead” James 2:17.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: It is forbidden for members to engage in sorcery as it negates the basic doctrinal principles of the Church

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: It is part of the biblical principle of the Church that the young ones must respect elders and members must give honour to their spiritual leaders. This is part of the instructions from the authors of scriptures through the inspiration of the Holy Spirit

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: In KICC/Kingdom teaching, supernatural beings do care about “proper ritual observance”, but KICC defines “ritual” very differently than traditional. KICC teaches “the supernatural is meant to be natural” but it still runs on laws/protocols. They call it “Kingdom culture” not “religious ritual” Example of such culture includes Communion, water baptism, laying on of hands, prayer/fasting patterns, giving tithes/offerings. These aren’t empty rituals, they’re legal entry points into the spirit realm. Angels are “executors of God’s word” Psalm 103:20, so when you follow God’s prescribed order, you give heaven legal ground to act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: To KICC it is believed and being taught that cleanliness is tantamount to Godliness

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Other members and non-members

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: It is believed in KICC that the punishment in the after life is more than mild sensory displeasure

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: This group does not belief in reincarnation.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: This group does not belief in reincarnation.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: KICC taught that the punishment in after life is harsh and eternal. It includes eternal condemnation and life in hell fire. A fire that is unquenchable and severe

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: It is believed in KICC that the punishment in the after life is more than mild sensory displeasure

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Eternity in condemnation and hell fire

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Especially in spiritual battles against spiritual battles

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Eternally reign with the supreme Being in his kingdom

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Eternal reign with the supreme being 9

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Eternal reign with the supreme being 9

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: KICC is a Pentecostal/charismatic church. Their entire doctrine is built on Jesus Christ as

Messiah/Savior. "Messianic" here means "centered on the Messiah" = Jesus. So yes, every teaching points back to Him

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: In KICC teaching, the Messiah's whereabouts now are known, but the timing of His coming is not. KICC teaches Jesus is at the right hand of the Father Heb 1:3, seated in glory, interceding for us Romans 8:34. KICC teaching says "Jesus is not on the cross anymore, He's on the throne." So His current location/location is clear: Heaven, reigning. KICC is firm on Matthew 24:36 – "But of that day and hour no one knows, not even the angels of heaven, nor the Son, but the Father only." They actively warn against date-setting. Their teachings say: "No man can predict the rapture. Anyone giving you a date is lying."

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, his first coming was to save the world from the consequences of sin, to set adherents free and offer salvation and new covenant. Whereas his second coming is to judge the whole world and to determine where human spend their eternity

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that the messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions and restores humanity back to God.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: sEY

Notes: He offers salvation to adherents and condemnation to those who reject his offer

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Kingsway International Christian Centre has a clear eschatology. KICC teaches that Jesus will physically return, there will be a rapture of believers, followed by tribulation, Christ's 1000-year reign, then a new heaven and new earth. He stresses that no one knows the timing, so the focus is on readiness through holy living, integrity, soul-winning, and faithful stewardship rather than predicting dates.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Though the church believes that Eschaton will be in the future, the time is not specified.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of the timing of the future here is figurative. Though they say it will happen at anytime, no one is sure about how soon or how far it will happen. Its nearness or distance is a matter that is figurative.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of the timing of the future here is figurative. Though they say it will happen at anytime, no one is sure about how soon or how far it will happen. Its nearness or distance is a matter that is figurative.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: In Kingsway teaching, believers don't do tasks to bring about the world's end. God alone controls the timing. The only "task" is readiness: live holy, be faithful, win souls, steward well while waiting.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: There shall be judgement of both alive and the dead

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: There shall be a new order in the new world

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: A political system set up and under God's control

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: The establishment of God's reign on earth and in the hearts of humanity.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: KICC teaches that adherent who act and behave according to the will of God will continue to live in the new kingdom which shall be forever.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those who live in the manner God desires.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Those who follow God in spirit and truth.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: sEetYhgIR

Notes: Righteous living and obedience of biblical instruction

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Kingsway prescribes general social norms around integrity, excellence, honesty, hard work, respect, and good citizenship. It doesn't enforce cultural rules on dress, music, or minor behaviors. The standard is "freedom with responsibility" – live decently so your life reflects Christ well.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Kingsway makes a distinction. *Morals* = fixed biblical standards like honesty, purity, integrity. Non-negotiable for all believers. *Conventions* = cultural/personal choices like dress, music, food. Flexible, based on freedom + responsibility + conscience. Ashimolowo's test: If Scripture doesn't forbid it and it doesn't damage your witness, it's convention, not moral law.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical

concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

Notes: It has connection

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: KICC core virtues include Integrity, excellence, faith, diligence, wisdom, and love. Character + high standards + hard work. Live honest, act excellent, trust God, serve people.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: KICC teaches Celibacy for singles, fidelity for the married. Purity outside marriage, freedom inside it.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: KICC teaches Celibacy for singles, fidelity for marrieds. Purity outside marriage, freedom inside it.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: KICC teaches Celibacy for singles, fidelity for marrieds. Purity outside marriage, freedom inside it.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Members can give willingly to the religious house as obligations

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: dOG Fo esuOh eHt OT

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: For church attendance, time of proselytising or evangelism, annual convention in a designated location and days of weekly or monthly worship

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Notes: Daily family prayer time which includes scripture reading and discussions is encouraged by the church leadership

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: They have branches in part of the western Africa and Europe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: KICC provides institutionalized famine relief through its charity arm and local church food banks in London and to members in Nigeria, plus food/water aid to famine zones in Africa via missions and partners. It's not a standalone "famine relief NGO", but practical food aid is built into their "faith with works" outreach model.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: KICC provides institutionalized poverty relief through its charity arm and local church food banks in London and to members in Nigeria, plus food/water aid to famine zones in Africa via missions and partners. It's not a standalone "famine relief NGO", but practical food aid is built into their "faith with works" outreach model.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: KICC provides institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm through its charity arm and local church food banks in London and to members in Nigeria, plus food/water aid to famine zones in Africa via missions and partners. It's not a standalone "famine relief NGO", but practical food aid is built into

their “faith with works” outreach model.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: KICC provides formal education through Kings University in Nigeria + Kings College of Excellence Bible School, plus tertiary-level training via Kingsway Leadership Institute and Canon Christian College. For adherents in the UK it runs Breaking Educational Barriers BEB: Oxbridge trips, university application workshops, and educational/career counselling, but it doesn't operate its own K-12 school.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Not restricted

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: members interact with KICC's bureaucracy through its departments and teams like Pastoral Care, Welfare, Noah's Ark food bank, and registration offices for membership, events, and aid. It's structured as "ministry departments" rather than red tape, so contact is usually with team leaders/pastors handling forms, counselling, or services.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: KICC members interact with outside bureaucracy through KICC's legal counselling, career advice, and welfare departments that help with housing, immigration, jobs, and government systems. The church provides guidance and support so members aren't navigating those systems alone.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, KICC provides a public food bank through its Noah's Ark Food Bank, which distributes food packages monthly at Prayer City and Walthamstow sites plus runs services in Grays and annual Christmas hampers. It's open to both members and non-members, Christians and non-Christians facing financial hardship.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members could access other forms of relief from the government and other institutions around them. The group's food banks and relief services are also open to both members and non-members, Christians and non-Christians facing financial hardship.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: No, KICC does not provide water management or utility services. Its public services focus on welfare, food bank, education, and counselling instead.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: KICC does not provide public transportation infrastructure like buses or roads. Its infrastructure is limited to church buildings and internal facilities for worship and community services.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are free to access public transport system as well as transport services run by private individuals and corporate organizations.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: No, KICC does not levy taxes since only governments have that authority. It does teach voluntary tithes and offerings - 10% of income plus donations from members, but these aren't mandatory charges on the public.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government levies taxes on all citizens and residents of Nigeria including the KICC members

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: KICC does not have an institutionalized police force. Only government authorities can operate police, and churches aren't allowed to. KICC does use trained security, ushers, and stewards for crowd

control and safety at services, but they cooperate with Nigerian police rather than replace them.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: No, KICC does not provide institutionalized judges or a court system. Only the state can appoint judges and run courts with legal authority to make binding rulings. KICC may offer pastoral counseling and internal church discipline for members, but those have no legal force and can't replace UK or Nigerian courts.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: KICC does not have an institutionalized military force. Only sovereign governments can legally maintain an army with weapons and combat authority, and religious organizations are not allowed to. KICC does employ security personnel and stewards to manage safety, parking, and crowd control at its services, but they are unarmed civilians who cooperate with Nigerian security agencies rather than operating as a military.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: No, KICC does not have its own distinct institutionalized language. It uses English as its main language of worship and administration, with translations into Yoruba, Igbo, French, Swahili, and others for its global congregation. While KICC has church-specific phrases like “grace card,” “seed sowing,” and “divine encounter” that function as internal jargon, these are just terms within English and not a separate language with unique grammar, syntax, or structure like Latin was for the Catholic Church.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group’s adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English Language which is the lingua francas

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group’s adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Yes, KICC does use a formal church calendar, but it’s built on the standard Gregorian calendar that the UK and Nigeria use. Their calendar is marked by recurring programs and events like the “January Fasting & Prayer,” “Holy Ghost Service,” “Shiloh,” and annual “Convention” at Prayer City. So while the dates follow the regular civil calendar, KICC layers its own ministry schedule and themes on top of it for planning services.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group’s adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: KICC doesn't provide free daily meals for all members, but it does provide food in specific settings. At events like Shiloh, Convention, and prayer retreats at Prayer City in Nigeria, they run cafeterias and food courts where attendees can buy meals, and sometimes provide meals to volunteers, staff, and guests. Outside of major programs, members handle their own food, though the church may organize outreach feeding programs for the needy in the community.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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